

Finding Meaning in This Time of Crisis: Contemporary Applications of Logotherapy

Cannon Fernandes SJ

Loyola Vikas Kendra, Mundgod

Abstract: Covid-19 pandemic has confined humans to follow social distancing and stay at home. Confining ourselves at home has made us to be in solitude and by ourselves. The new generations are not attuned to be in solitude as it pierces their very existence of finding meaning. According to one survey the suicide and criminal rates were on the rise during this pandemic. What gives us meaning? Is it our wealth or our parents or our social media friends? Each life is precious. Suffering or solitude cannot take away our will for living and being cheerful. This write-up will enlighten our minds and hearts to find meaning and value our lives.

Keywords: Meaninglessness, Logotherapy, Happiness, Meaning, pleasure, power, determinants, suffering, encountering, experiencing, psychotherapy, depression, suicide, trauma, mental, co-relation.

Introduction

Meaninglessness is a frequent visitor to the therapist's consulting room. A sense of meaninglessness is by no means always bundled with searching for God or losing religious belief. It could manifest itself simply as a certain inner emptiness, a feeling that some vital ingredient has gone missing from our life. Particularly in these 'age of Gadgets' we find there is something lacking

in our life. However, we have temporary companions in the form of electronic gadgets (smart phones, tabs, laptops etc.). These gadgets try to give us the interim happiness and companionship. But, they lack in the perpetual happiness which is possible only through us. To solve this mystery of meaninglessness Logotherapy comes into play. Logotherapy a concept developed by the famous 20th century neurologist and psychiatrist Victor Frankl etymologically means ‘meaning therapy’. Before Victor Frankl, Sigmund Freud spoke about humans ‘will to pleasure’ and Alfred Adler culling from Nietzsche spoke about the ‘will to Power’. Meaning plays an important role in each one life. Some find meaning in their profession and some find meaning in the miniscule work they do. Ultimately, it is the meaning or the goal in life that keeps us going. Suicides are in great number because of this loss of meaning. We feel that we do not belong to this world once we lose meaning in our lives. Logotherapy is based on the existential analysis of Soren Kierkegaard’s ‘will to meaning’. According to him meaning is not equal to knowledge but meaning is a lived experience and a quest to find one’s values, beliefs and purpose in meaningless world. As a staunch Christian this meaning comes through the word of God.

Some Features of Logotherapy

Victor Frankl’s Logotherapy was founded on the belief that the primary motivational force is to find meaning in life. Furthermore, life has meaning under all circumstances, even the most miserable ones. We all have freedom to find meaning in what we do and experience. According to him Human spirit is not spiritual but the will of human being. He emphasizes on the search for meaning which is not equal to God or supernatural being. However, there are barriers of affluence, Hedonism, materialism etc. Frankl observed all these during his stay at the Nazi concentration camp where he saw humans’ pursuit of pleasure and acquiring and consuming material

goods. We humans discover meaning by creating work or doing a deed, by experiencing something or encountering something and by the attitude we take toward unavoidable suffering. We know everything can be taken from a man except one thing, and that thing is human freedom. Human freedom is the key we possess. So, we are the masters of our own life. If we are depressed in life we need to try to see the reality from the others perspective and balance the matter in an equivalence.

Frankl believed in three core properties on which his theory and therapy were based:

1. Each person has a healthy core.
2. One's primary focus is to enlighten others to their own internal resources and provide them tools to use their inner core.
3. Life offers purpose and meaning but does not promise fulfilment or happiness

Going a step further, Logotherapy proposes that meaning in life can be discovered in three distinct ways:

1. By creating a work or doing a deed.
2. By experiencing something or encountering someone.
3. By the attitude that we take toward unavoidable suffering.

Importance of Logotherapy

Logotherapy as will to meaning is the only psychotherapy because there is no psychotherapy other than theory of man. Though Freud and Adler spoke extensively about 'will to pleasure and power' respectively, yet they fail to affirm because they try to project human existence negatively. Therefore, existentialism plays an important

role here. It's existentialism not of machine model or rat model but of freedom. In his observations at the Nazi camp Frankl saw that humans can never be free from every condition- there are biological, sociological and psychological determinants. However, Humans are capable of resisting and braving even the worst conditions. For this to happen humans have to detach from situations, choose an attitude about him/her, determine his/her own determinants and shape his/her character. Finally, we are individually responsible for our own life.

Practicality

Frankl even used this therapy practically in a number of occasions. For example to relieve the stress of pilots it was told to the pilots just before the flight to know the purpose of the journey. A greater result was observed. Moreover, there was a highest enthusiasm seen during these things. According to Frankl, Depression has three dimensions- psychological, physiological and spiritual. Psychologically we feel depressed because feelings of depression root from undertaking tasks beyond our abilities. When we fail and get discouraged we feel depressed. For example, in the game of football when someone misses a goal he feels depressed and loses his confidence. Physiologically we feel something called “Vital Low” which diminishes our physical energy. Spiritually there is a tension between who he actually is in relation to what he should be. For example, in religious life very often we mask our life at some moment of time.

“A therapy for the sick, support for the sufferer, education for the confused, and philosophy for the frustrated ... logotherapy has developed methods for working with clients who suffer from phobias in their sexual behavior, have incurable diseases, or lead empty and meaningless lives” (Faramarzi & Bavali, 2017). This shows the variety of contexts logotherapy can be applied to.

Logotherapy can be used by itself to treat a mental health disorder, as most early psychotherapy was used. It can also be used in a positive psychology context to help people with no discernible mental health disorders live a life with meaning, and in turn higher levels of well-being. Logotherapy can also be used in a group or family therapy setting to help people deal with a number of stressors. The versatility of logotherapy is clear when looking through its modern-day applications. Logotherapy has recently been used to help support students, whether it's in the context of giving elementary school students a sense of meaning and lowering their levels of depression, or in the context of giving first-year University students logotherapy-based support. Logotherapy has also been used to improve the quality of life of adolescents with terminal cancer. Logotherapy has further been advocated as a treatment for trauma

Criticism

Frankl was not without his critics. Some felt he used his time in the Nazi camps as a way to promote his brand of psychotherapy, and others felt his support came only from religious leaders in the United States (indeed, he did recruit ministers and pastoral psychologists to work with him).

In 1961, his ideas were challenged by psychologist Rollo May, known as the founder of the existential movement in the United States, who argued that logotherapy was equivalent to authoritarianism, with the therapist dictating solutions to the patient. In this way, it was felt that the therapist diminished the patient's responsibility in finding solutions to problems. It is not clear, however, whether this was a fundamental problem of logotherapy, or a failing of

Frankl as a therapist himself, as he was said to be arrogant in his manner of speaking to patients.

In this way, it may be that logotherapy argues that there are always clear solutions to problems and that the therapist has the task of finding these for the client. However, Frankl argued that logotherapy actually educates the patient to take responsibility. Regardless, it is clear that in the application of Frankl's theories, it is important to highlight that the patient must be a participant rather than a recipient in the process

In Everyday Life

How might you apply the principles of logotherapy to improve your everyday life?

- **Create something.** Just as Frankl suggested, creating something (e.g., art) gives you a sense of purpose, which can add meaning to your life.
- **Develop relationships.** The supportive nature of spending time with others will help you to develop more of a sense of meaning in your life.
- **Find purpose in pain.** If you are going through something bad, try to find a purpose in it. Even if this is a bit of mental trickery, it will help to see you through. For example, if a family member is going through medical treatments for a disease, view your purpose as being there to support that person.
- **Understand that life is not fair.** There is nobody keeping score, and you will not necessarily be dealt a fair deck. However, life can always have meaning, even in the worst of situations.
- **Freedom to find meaning.** Remember that you are always free to make meaning out of your life situation. Nobody can take that away from you.

- **Focus on others.** Try to focus outside of yourself to get through feeling stuck about a situation.
- **Accept the worst.** When you go out seeking the worse, it reduces the power that it has over you.

Survey Results

A systematic review of research evidence pertaining to logotherapy conducted in 2016 found correlations or effects pertaining to logotherapy in the following areas or for the following conditions:

- Correlation between presence of meaning in life, search for meaning in life, and life satisfaction, happiness
- Lower meaning in life among patients with mental disorders
- Search for meaning and presence of meaning as a resilience factor
- Correlation between meaning in life and suicidal thoughts in cancer patients
- Effectiveness of a logotherapy program for early adolescents with cancer
- Effectiveness of logotherapy on depression in children
- Effectiveness of logotherapy in reducing job burnout, empty nest syndrome
- Correlation with marital satisfaction

Conclusion

We know goals are unreachable. When we chase these unreachable goals we are sure to fail. Furthermore, we lose a sense of future and meaning and go into depression. Logotherapy – a positive psychotherapy comes into the

picture in this situation. Sigmund Freud and Alfred Adler had a negative connotation in their theories of human man, but Frankl makes human being a positive one. That is the greatness of this therapy. So, logotherapy is a beautiful therapy to make a positive impact of human existence.

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Cannon Fernandes SJ was a student of JDV from 2017-19. Presently he is the Assistant Director at Loyola Vikas Kendra- Centre for Social Action Mundgod, Karnataka. He is fond of learning new things every day and keeps himself updated with the world news. He loves to read in his free time and he is a musician. E-mail: cannonfernssj@gmail.com

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